

The Dictionary in S,M,L,XL

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Prelude: The Rhizome – the reordering of things

„This Massive Book is a Novel about Architecture“ is the first sentence on the back of *S,M,L,XL*, metallic-matte envelope, a book cover that reflects and diffuses its context. The pages show an extensive accumulation of material produced by OMA. This material, whether previously published as independent essays or as documentation of theoretical and built projects, has been re-organized, re-positioned, re-related and re-framed into a new composite body. As a self-declared novel, this body of work makes no claim to the factual, but unfolds a range of subjectivities — from semiotic chains into a web of multiplicities.¹ These semiotic chains are formed by sequences of images and texts: sometimes symbolic, sometimes indexical, sometimes images pose as text or text poses as image. These images and texts are subjected to a series of manipulations that operate an encyclopedic range of transformations,² performing extractions and integrations, dis-positionings and superimpositions — and, as a result, transversing information and weaving patterns. It “establishes connections between organizations of power, and circumstances relative to the arts, sciences, and social struggles,”³ which, as the book cover states, “illuminates the condition of architecture today.”⁴

The margins of the book included a continues dictionary, which is probably the most noticeable feature of *S,M,L,XL*. The dictionary is a paratext and so are many texts in the book. Paratexts are small peripheral texts which mediate between writer and reader. They are neither truly inside or outside the book, they operate on the threshold of interpretation.⁵ In this case the dictionary entries are not just definitions, but citations, which carry the voices of philosophers, cultural and political figures and seemingly random talking heads. The embedded quotations in the dictionary introduce voices as

1 Deleuze describes Michel Foucault's *The Archaeology of Knowledge* (1969) as "the most decisive step yet taken in the theory-practice of multiplicities." Bové, Foreword *The Foucault Phenomenon : the Problematics of Style*:14

2 Gerard Genette summarizes literary transformations of existing texts in his book *Palimpseste: Die Literatur auf zweiter Stufe*. Among them: stylistic, semantic, pragmatic and thematic transformations and transpositions. But also Contractions, substitutions, unfoldings, etc. Usually transforming one or more original texts. A theme that – through analogy with architectural design could get more attention. The analogy between language and architecture often stays on the level of the metaphorical, but rarely makes methodical comparisons. If they do, they get little attention.

3 Deleuze, Gilles, and Félix Guattari. *A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*, p. 28.

4 See covertext of *S,M,L,XL*

5 Genette, *Paratexts: Thresholds of Interpretation*.

Paratextual elements can be compared to architectural elements at the thresholds of buildings — such as windows, stairs, entrances, corridors, doorbells, plinths, columns, porticos, pediments, and doormats. The perimeter of the text resembles the perimeter of a building and its envelope. As with paratexts, these architectural features mediate the constitution and communication of character and identity. Paratexts hint at content and program. A further exploration of the articulation of borders and thresholds in buildings produced by OMA could be meaningful.

marginalia, as commentary. It stratifies certain speech types and alludes to their influences on culture and on the creative thinking of Rem Koolhaas and OMA.

Their defining descriptions come from writers such as Umberto Eco, Charles Jencks, Roland Barthes, Robert Venturi, Denise Scott Brown, Michel Foucault, Gilles Deleuze, and Félix Guattari, not to forget the occasional TV personality such as Donald Trump.⁶ Many definitions carry voices from structuralist, postmodern and deconstructivist architectural discourse, but broadly they range across sources as diverse as literature, art, advertising, pop culture, semiotics, and even the AutoCAD Reference Manual. The entries include words such as “Body,” “Pop,” “Popular,” “Zoom,” “Information,” and “Rhizome.”⁷

Its definitions read as affectionate thoughts, small distractions, introspective murmurs, ironic comments, or subjective variations on the architectural practice and lexicon. The transformation of clear definitions into suggestive fragments creates a sense of speech and evokes associations that destabilize the dictionary’s defining function. It gives the impression of an alphabetized stream of consciousness and creates a sense of narrative voice, auto-communication, and indirect as-well-as inner discourse. The opposition between diegetic and non-diegetic, between elements that exist within the world of the story and those that come from outside it, mix and influence each other. The representation of the narrated world’s interior and exterior fades and is in constant dialogue. The boundaries between subjective and objective become blurred. The dictionary is transformed from a scientific device into a literary tool.

In its vast connectiveness, the book as a whole, but especially the dictionary, resembles the *rhizome*, a concept borrowed from botany and appropriated by Deleuze and Guattari in *A Thousand Plateaus*. Deleuze and Guattari use the term to describe a broader set of structural phenomena: they present the rhizome as a literary category, associate it with maps, and compare it to symbiotic relationships between distinct organisms, such as flowers and bees.⁸ In botany, the rhizome describes a network of roots, nodes and stems that enables the horizontal and independent proliferation of certain plant species. The rhizome builds large underground networks, allowing plants to sprout from multiple locations, which in turn grow more roots. It is both a method of energy storage and a strategy of re-

6 The source information in S,M,L,XL’s dictionary is placed in an index at the back of the book.

7 See Koolhaas, *S,M,L,XL*.

8 Deleuze, Gilles, and Félix Guattari. *A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*, p. 28.

production. But most of all, the Rhizome is a metaphor which describes the structural proliferation of knowledge through associations of all kinds. Proliferations that are neither linear nor tree-like.⁹ It is a structure of thought that harnesses poetic registers through openness. The rhizome proposes a mode of thought where everything speaks, and disciplinary boundaries - or indeed any boundaries - are deterritorialized.

At some point, Rem Koolhaas himself uttered the fear of becoming Deleuzian, expressing that it “might already be too late”¹⁰ Additionally, S,M,L,XL seems close to Deleuze's ideal book. A book that “[...] lay everything out on a plane of exteriority of this kind, on a single page, the same sheet: lived events, historical determinations, concepts, individuals, groups, social formations.”¹¹ It is what S,M,L,XL aspires to do, with the many different images, text types, the dictionary, and the multitude of their appearances, all functioning as nodes: they weave lines of thought, link ideas, people and places through associations, metaphors, resemblances and analogies.

9 The idea of the Rhizome has attracted interest in the field of educational sciences. The rhizome breaks radically with the scientific categorical structures described by Michel Foucault; in that sense, it can be seen as a continuation of his thinking.

10 See also: Graafland, “Koolhaas en de *City of Flows*”; Lueder, “Proximity: The Unfolding of a Koolhaasian Hypothesis in Book Space and Architectural Space”; and Hsu, “The Revolutionary (Re)Vision of Modern Architecture: Rem Koolhaas, from Surrealism to the Structuralist Activity.”

11 Deleuze, Gilles, and Guattari, Félix. “Introduction: Rhizome,” in *A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*, p. 9.

Koolhaas and 68

Rem Koolhaas began his career as a journalist in 1963 at the *Haagse Post*. Here he conducted interviews with artists, while also studying Scriptwriting in Amsterdam.¹² In 1968 he started studying architecture at the AA in London. Here Charles Jencks introduced him to surrealism, structuralism and Saussurean Semiology.¹³

That year large civil protests erupted in the streets of Paris. Nanterre, a suburb of Paris, became the cradle of May '68.¹⁴ The university looked similar to the grey monotone architecture, which surrounded it, and it soon became a symbol of a bureaucratic education on a mass scale, housed in concrete buildings with poor facilities and supposed, but little actual student participation. At first students, who were over crowding the university wanted educational reform, but the ideological scope behind the protests grew. Soon the protests spread to Paris, to the Sorbonne. Here the protests, coincidentally with large worker strikes. A strange combination of contradictory voices, of people who either rejected or wanted to participate in the post-war consumer culture. The protests grew to be against social segregation, against bureaucracy, against consumerism. Instead they opted for meaning and imagination.¹⁵ In Paris proper, the *École des Beaux-Arts* was turned in a printing shop and renamed into the *Atelier Populaire*, which produced large amounts of provocative posters. The streets became a medium of communication through graffiti, with slogans such as "poetry is in the streets," and "imagination is not a gift, it must be conquered" painted on public surfaces like the walls of the *Odéon* in Paris. Many French philosophers, theorists and writers - including Baudrillard, Lyotard, Virilio, Derrida, Foucault, Deleuze, and Felix Guattari - participated in the protests.¹⁶ Their ideas influenced the revolutionary atmosphere, and the world of art and design did not stay untouched. Exhibition venues, such as the *Milan Triennale* and *Venice Biennale*, were occupied; paintings were hung upside down and objects were turned around.¹⁷

12 Böck, *Six Canonical Projects by Rem Koolhaas*, p. 25

13 Hsu, *The Revolutionary (Re) Vision of Modern Architecture: Rem Koolhaas, from Surrealism to the Structuralist Activity*, p. 24

14 Horn, *The Spirit of '68: Rebellion in Western Europe and North America, 1956-1976*, p. 103

15 In 1968, there was an accumulation of events and improbable convolutions. Robert Kennedy and Martin Luther King were assassinated. The Vietnam war was attracting popular resentment.

16 Feedberg, D., and Freedman, R. *When Poetry Ruled the Streets*, p. 19.

17 See Grima, *The Italian Avant-Garde, 1968-1976*

In 1969, Dutch writer Cees Nootboom won the country's top journalism award for his report on the Paris revolts, an experimental collage of captions, quotes, and statements that captured the era's conflicting voices and chaotic atmosphere.¹⁸

18 Harbers, Felix, and Broersma, Marcel. "Personal Journalism Against the Current: Cees Nootboom, the Paris Revolt and New Journalism in the Netherlands," p. 30.

Towards 1968

French intellectual culture had been rich and complex in the years before the revolts. A growing circle of thinkers had begun to question the authority of established systems of meaning and classification. Claude Lévi-Strauss would dissect the cultures of meaning, the semiotic regimes, of societies untouched by western scientific ideas or media. Roland Barthes turned an anthropologic gaze towards the Myths and systems of meaning in popular culture, showing the codes of everyday images. Umberto Eco developed a theories of semiotics, while Foucault interrogated how classificatory systems produce and regulate forms of subjectivity.

Prominent contemporary thinkers and writers such as Roland Barthes, Jacques Derrida, Julia Kristeva, Gérard Genette, Georges Bataille, Umberto Eco and Michel Foucault —who feature in the dictionary of S, M, L, XL had found a platform for their ideas in the journal *Tel Quel*.¹⁹ The Journal, *Tel Quel* had been founded a few years prior, in 1960. It focused on semiotics, psychoanalysis, as well as language, its structure, textuality and intertextuality. The journal offered a platform for the semiotic investigations of Foucault, Barthes, and Kristeva, and became a hub for what can be called, more generally, structuralist thought. Many contributions elevated literature to the status of a science and confronted science with the literary. It also saw the text as a place of ideological confrontations. While the Situationists, under the direction of Guy Debord, put forward a protest against the objectification of everyday life, which they saw to be the result of an increasingly capitalist and functionalistic culture. Intellectuals and Artists around *Tel Quel* and the Situationists had helped shape the ground for the type of criticism, which fueled 68. These literary groups often drew on surrealist methods, of fragment and collage.

Towards 68, the question arose if meaning itself could be made open, unstable - even appropriated as a tool of revolt? In 1962, Umberto Eco - medievalist, semiotician, novelist, contributor to *Tel Quel* and friend of Michel Foucault — published *Opera Aperta* (The Open Work), a book in which he examines openness in texts and describes the concept as decisive for the possibilities of interpretation. The concept of openness is determined by the quantity and diversity of information — in other words, its semantic plurality. It can be understood as a constellation of positions within a field of re-

¹⁹ French, Roland, and Roland-François. *The Tel Quel Reader*, p. 5.

lations, where the configuration of balance and disorder of information generates the poetic capacities within the text.²⁰

A few years later, in 1966 Michel Foucault, also a contributor to *Tel Quel*, published *Les mots et les choses – une archéologie des sciences humaines* (The Order of Things: An Archaeology of the Human Sciences). The book unfolds a genealogy of human knowledges, taking the 15th century as its starting point and tracing transformations of scientific understanding up to the turn of the 20th century. Foucault describes 15th-century modes of thought that are based on similarities and expressed, one could say, through chains of associations, which shift towards a structural understanding of the world in differences, expressed through taxonomies and tables. *Les mots et les choses* describes and simultaneously questions the modalities and coherences of classifications — a central theme for the development of the sciences. Foucault compares and opposes modern scientific orders of classification to narrative and subjective structures of coherence that had been more prevalent in earlier epistemes. Foucault describes a time when myth had a place alongside ratio, and a time when ratio became the dominant form of understanding. Earlier knowledge, as Foucault says, “therefore consisted in relating one form of language to another form of language; in restoring the great, unbroken plain of words and things; in making everything speak.”²¹ In other words, science tends to close rather than open the dialogic potential through its ambition to define.

In 1967 (a year after *The Order of Things* is published in Paris) Roland Barthes states that the idea of the Lexicon is in a crisis in many fields of research, saying that: “the regular correspondence between signifier and signified is being disrupted.”²² Lexicons and dictionaries are under scrutiny as Lexicographers realize that detailed information and contextual relationships among lexical items are often neglected. As Harold Conklin Observes in 1969:

20 A jump could be possible here to the notion of intertextuality of Julia Kristeva who described it “as the transposition of one or more systems of signs into another, accompanied by a new articulation of the enunciative and denotative position. Any SIGNIFYING PRACTICE (q. v.) is a field (in the sense of space traversed by lines of force) in which various signifying systems undergo such a transposition.” Gerard Genette offers a similar but slightly different definition of the concept: “as a relationship of co presence between two texts or among several texts: that is to say, eidetically and typically as the actual presence of one text within another. In its most explicit and literal form, it is the traditional practice of quoting.” The idea of intertextuality is interesting here because it literally opens the text and offers paths of association. Where other associations in the “space traversed by lines” might be more individual or contextual.

21 Foucault, Michel. *The Order of Things: An Archaeology of the Human Sciences*, p. 44.

22 Barthes: *Semiotics and Urbanism*, p. 15.

“While extant dictionaries and vocabularies do provide glosses and definitional material, many of the non-trivial, and often essential, semantic and contextual relationships obtaining among lexical items are often neglected or handled in an imprecise and unsystematic way.”²³

Roland Barthes tried to imagine alternative types of lexicons to imbue the words we use and the things we look at with new meaning, and by doing so he fantasized about different possible relations between words and things.

Umberto Eco went a step further and exposed the architectural element to a direct semiotic analysis. Not as metaphorical exercise, but by studying direct analogies between material and linguistic components. Not architecture like a language, but architecture as language. With the architectural unit as a syntax system and the individual elements as lexical units. Eco summarizes the question as follows:

“To transpose linguistic concepts into the terminology of architectural semiotics, one would have to ask: 'what is an architectural " word" '?..... and thus 'what sign-vehicles in architecture communicate a specifically architectural meaning?'.²⁴

In *Les mots et les choses*, Foucault similarly argues for the associative power of narrative modes of knowledge against the strict orders of classification imposed by science, while Umberto Eco's idea of openness describes how a text's semantic plurality expands its poetic capacity. Together, these French literary circles explored the fragile boundary between narrative and science through experimental writing and thematic transgressions, just as New Journalism broke open the scientific ideal of objectivity by weaving narration into reportage. Cees Noteboom's exemplary reporting, composed as a bricolage of quotations and fragments, placed the responsibility for meaning on the reader and directly questioned the neutral role of the journalist. There is also a striking similarity, between his reportage and the dictionary in *S,M,L,XL*, although it might be somewhat coincidental, in that they are both products of the same revolutionary time.

23 McArthur: *Worlds of Reference: Lexicography, Learning and Language from the Clay Tablet to the Computer*, p. 144.

24 Eco: *A Componential Analysis of the Architectural Sign /Column/*, p. 96.

French Theory and the Crisis of the Lexicon

Not only revolution travelled the world, so did French theory.

In 1969, Charles Jencks helped Semiotics and Structural Anthropology enter Architectural discourse through the publication of *Meaning in Architecture*. The layout allowed a form of a debate and the margins were used to introduce commentary and critique, giving the book the sense of a debate or dialogue. The semiotic concepts of Barthes were extensively discussed. Doing so, the publication offered a voice to many authoritative architects and architectural critics, about the question of meaning in architecture. The publication would become an important transmitter of ideas and a transitioning moment towards what Jencks would later Call Post-Modern Architecture.

In 1968, tenants started to leave Pruitt-Igoe, which was blown up in 1972. That year, Rem Koolhaas studied at Cornell, where he was a student of Oswald Mathias Ungers, who had gotten the chair of architecture in 1968. Ungers had “fled Germany”, perhaps as a response to the increasingly politicized climate around the student protests.²⁵ Ungers introduced Koolhaas to Foucault, who gave seminars at the university and spend a year “immersed in French intellectual culture” after he had already spend considerable time researching Roland Barthes.²⁶

To test the linguistic analogy, Charles Jencks ventured into a Semantic Analysis of Stirling's Olivetti Centre²⁷ In 1974 at a Lecture at the Architectural Association he asks people which metaphor they found most appropriate, in other words, he sets out to see what semantic chains come forth as associations after looking at architecture. Some people perceived it as “a series of stacked, plastic trash-cans”, where others hold more positive views. Formal and material associations with other objects, such as trains and buses evoke associations such as “futuristic” or “machine aesthetics”. Adjectival attributes such as “large”, “plastic” and “rounded” are seen as the sum of elements that bring forward metaphors. These are the building blocks of interpretation through association. “Buildings are perceived semantically by chains of thought, governed by comparisons, analogies, metaphors and the overall search for similarities.”²⁸

25 Schrijver, *Oswald Mathias Ungers and Rem Koolhaas*, 24

26 Miljacki et al., “2 Architects 10 Questions: On Program — Rem Koolhaas + Bernard Tschumi.”, 11

27 Jencks, *A Semantic Analysis of Stirling's Olivetti Centre Wing*, p. 238.

Charles Jencks furthers the analogy by remarking that “when a column can be thought of as a word, a phrase and a building can become a whole novel.” This linguistic analogy thus has important implications for understanding narrative in architecture.

28 Idem.:237

Academic interest from the late 1960s can be characterized as a “search for new vocabularies”. Robert Venturi and Scot Brown search in Las Vegas and in Pop Culture, while referring back to the aesthetic theories of victorian gothic, which is full of linguistic analogies. Reyner Banham travelled to Los Angeles, while Aldo van Eyck looked at the Architecture of the Dogon People and Allison and Peter Smithson searched for found objects. Christopher Alexander on the other hand, works with semantic structures and mathematical strategies to construct a “Pattern Language”.

There is an intensified critique on modernism and on academic practices around the same time that the lexicon is under professional scrutiny. Perhaps one could even say that both critical situations signify a sense that there was a lack of interest for the depth and the possible ambiguities of meaning.

It is in this line that Charles Jencks criticises contemporary architecture for its deficit in articulate architecture and overall lack of attention for the question of meaning in Architecture. He characterizes modern architecture for its “obsessive concentration on indexical meanings”²⁹ and states that “modern architecture has built up a lexicon of prefabricated details and clichés”³⁰. He even goes as far as to say that it “promotes a banal and literalist life of simplified functionality”³¹. The crisis of modern architecture echos the crisis of the lexicon. Both are criticized for a neglect of connotation. The world has come to requests poetry rather than prose.

29 See Jencks: *Semiology and Architecture*.

30 Jencks: *The Architectural Sign*, p. 86.

31 *Idem.*:107

Exodus

Koolhaas's response was not one of metaphor, or vernacular, but by exploring exactly that, which had been discredited, the city. "I don't agree with Jencks's criticism of modern architecture."³²

His project "Exodus, or the Voluntary Prisoners of Architecture" was first an Entry for Casabella's 1972 competition "The City as Meaningful Environment" and then became his final project at the Architectural Association in London.³³ This project phantasised about a city, which would be the mirror image of desolation, division, aggression, and instead proposed a city, of invention, where new forms of behaviour were tested, and which brought to the surface hidden motivations, desires and impulses. It was also the mirror image of all that was assumed bad about urban sprawl and the hubris of modern urban planning. Soon, in 1975 OMA was established, together with the Greek architect Elia Zenghelis, Zoe Zenghelis, his then wife, Madelon Vriesendorp, who would later make the iconic paintings for *Delirious New York*. Ungers was also on the List.³⁴ A year later, published in 1978, Koolhaas's Thesis, *Delirious New York: A Retroactive Manifesto for Manhattan*, described New York, as a product, not of rational and socialist urban planning, but of subconscious, even surrealist processes, brought forwards by a capitalist driven economy of desire.

Both *Exodus* and *Delirious New York* had swallowed the postmodern flair, and not long after, in *La condition postmoderne: Rapport sur le savoir* (The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge) published in 1979, Jean-François Lyotard suggests that "science has always been in conflict with narratives"³⁵ and argues that narrative knowledge fundamentally opposes scientific knowledge. This tension — often reduced to a commonplace feature of postmodernism — marks a defining element in the heterogeneity and contradictions of postmodern discourse itself. The dichotomy between narrative and scientific knowledge recurs in the positions taken by *Tel Quel*, in the constrained yet generative writing methods of *OuLiPo*, and in the Situationists' activist tactics. It is French Theory and the movement of 68, whose traces are found everywhere in the work of Rem Koolhaas.

32 Koolhaas, *The Sparkling Metropolis & Delirious New — A Repository of Forms*,

33 Koolhaas, *S,M,L,XL*

34 Schrijver, *Oswald Mathias Ungers and Rem Koolhaas*, 14

35 Lyotard, Jean-François. *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge*, p. 21.

Rem Koolhaas and the search for new vocabularies

In 1995, after a few years of professional practice, and a few real architectural projects, *S,M,L,XL* was published. The book collects the projects of O.M.A., but also the writings of Koolhaas, some of his student projects, manifestos and short essays.

The rhizomatic approach to information, does not halt at the confines of *S,M,L,XL*, but can be projected on the working methods of OMA and the research projects in which Rem Koolhaas has been involved in since the publication of *S,M,L,XL*. The Elements of Architecture exhibition at the Venice Biennial, for example, aimed to lay bare the modern lexicon of the 20th Century through an encyclopedic summary of architectural elements such as “stairs”, “elevators”, “roofs” and “balconies”. Another accumulative work, *Project of the City*, undertaken with Harvard students is an ongoing project that produces a series of publications, all with an individual theme. The publication collects information on themes such as: “The Crystal Palace”, “The Escalator”, “Air Conditioning” and “Consumer Marketing”. The Project of the City collects large amounts of information and re-positions and re-relates them to learn “new vocabularies”.

As with *S,M,L,XL* these projects experiment with indexing techniques, summaries and lists. The projects bring together information and presents it with chronologies, essays, scientific comparisons and essayist narratives. Like *S,M,L,XL* collects words such as ‘Body’, ‘Pop’, ‘Popular’, ‘Zoom’, ‘Rhizome’ and ‘Information’. So do exhibitions like the Elements of Architecture and publications from the Project of the City, intend to lay bare architectural vocabularies. The accumulative effort of Rem Koolhaas and the different participating academics, their students, the organization of exhibitions and the publications that they are involved in, seem to have developed into a continues project. A large encyclopedic endeavour, that collects, re-articulates, re-relates and occasionally bombards the existing with new meaning.

But what is the sense of this? Oswald Matthias Ungers, Koolhaas’ old teacher articulated an interesting critique on the absence of criteria in the collective spirit of Rem Koolhaas:

“He tries to transform the consumer-attitude into an artistic expression. He will never end this because he is always concerned with updating. There's no stability, no criterion to it. It's like collecting data all the time, you never come to a conclusion. They are already obsolete

before you can do so. Koolhaas is creating obsolete architecture. He's surfing on the Zeitgeist."³⁶

If Koolhaas does or doesn't create obsolete architecture? The polysemic effects of S,M,L,XL and the abundance of relations that are established oscillate between critical thought and what Ungers calls a "consumer-attitude". It destabilizes the viewers position. The spectator moves between modalities, forms and types, from one hybrid to another. Clear definitions or careful singular critiques are a few. Sometimes, or often even, a powerful observation is articulated, but just to leave you with a sense of doubt. Interpretation is pushed between mathesis and poesis, from truth to fiction. What are you looking at, a Duck or a Rabbit?

The french encyclopedists intended to "illuminate" their world through rational thought, through the careful collection of information, documentation and classification of things and ideas. The Rhizome transposes signifying practices. It is a tool to create openness in the existing relations between words and things. The dictionary in S,M,L,XL isn't there to describe, it's there to make everything speak and to invite the viewer into the phenomenon of unlimited semiosis, through a web of intertextual paths and along the chatter of heteroglossia.

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